

TEACHING PORTFOLIO

Jess Beck

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I. Courses Taught and Prepared to Teach

* = Syllabus included in teaching portfolio

Courses Taught

Harvard University

*ANTHRO 1033 – Archaeology of Inequality

Instructor of Record (IR). Lecture and discussion focused class for majors and non-majors. In F2021 both undergraduate and graduate students enrolled; could be taught as a lower-level lecture or an upper-level seminar in future.

ANTHRO 1201 – Human Osteology & Bioarchaeology

ANTHRO 1058/2058 – Bias in Archaeology

Vassar College

ANTH 239 – Forensic Anthropology and Bioarchaeology,

IR. Six-week, 200-level Anthropology course, for majors and non-majors.

ANTH 229 – Skeletal Anatomy

IR. Six-week, 200-level Anthropology course, for majors and non-majors. Pre-requisite for ANTH 239.

*ANTH 130 – Archaeology: Lessons from the Past

IR. Introduction to Archaeology, 100-level Anthropology course for majors and non-majors.

*ANTH 170-52 – From Artifacts to Arguments: Introduction to the Archaeology of Prehistoric Europe

IR. First-Year Writing Seminar for majors and non-majors. Taught partially remotely due to COVID-19 pandemic.

ANTH 170-03 – Written in Bone: Using Human Skeletons to Understand the Ancient Past

IR. First-Year Writing Seminar for majors and non-majors.

University of Pittsburgh

ANTH 2536 – Inequality and the Body in Archaeology and Bioarchaeology

Co-taught with fellow faculty member as IRs. Upper-level or graduate seminar.

University of Michigan

ANTHRARC 296 – The Science of Skeletons: Introduction to Bioarchaeology

IR; For non-majors and majors.

ANTHRBIO 364 – Nutrition and Human Evolution

Graduate Student Instructor (GSI); Professor Maureen Devlin; For non-majors and majors.

ANTHRBIO 368 – Primate Social Behavior

GSI; Professor John Mitani; For non-majors and majors.

ANTHRBIO 161 – Introduction to Biological Anthropology

GSI; Professor John Mitani; For non-majors and majors.

ANHRBIO 467 – Human Behavioral Ecology

GSI; Professor Beverly Strassman; For non-majors and majors.

ANTHRBIO 365 – Human Evolution

GSI; Professor Milford Wolpoff; For non-majors and majors.

Courses Prepared to Teach

ANTHRO 1201 – Human Osteology and Bioarchaeology

Preparing to teach as IR in S2022 at Harvard. For graduate students and undergraduate students. Open to majors and non-majors.

ANTHRO 1058 / 2058 – Bias in Archaeology

Preparing to co-teach with Rowan Flad as IRs in S2022 at Harvard. For graduate students and undergraduate students. Targeted at Anthropology or Studies of Women, Gender, and Sexuality students.

Introduction to Biological Anthropology

Given previous teaching experience in biological anthropology I could prepare to teach this course for non-majors and majors from all subfields.

II. Teaching Awards

Harvard University Bok Center for Research and Teaching, Certificate of Teaching Excellence
For “Archaeology of Inequality” in Fall 2021. This certificate recognizes instructors who have received a score of 4.50 or higher (out of 5.00) in the “overall” category of the Q Guide from five or more respondents.

U-M Rackham Outstanding Graduate Student Instructor Award
One of 20 awarded annually, \$1000 award.

U-M Department of Anthropology Outstanding Teaching Award
For “Nutrition and Human Evolution” in Winter 2014.

U-M Department of Anthropology Innovative Teaching Award
For “Human Evolution” in Fall 2011.

III. Evidence of Teaching Effectiveness
(Full evaluations for all other courses taught as instructor of record included in Appendix A)

Quantitative Evaluations 2010-2014

Course	Overall, the instructor was an excellent teacher.	The instructor stressed important points in lectures/discussions.	The instructor made good use of examples and illustrations.	The instructor put material across in an interesting way.	Instructor appeared to have a thorough knowledge of the subject.	The instructor seemed well prepared for each class.	Response Rate
Nutrition and Human Evolution (Winter 2014)	4.68	4.56	4.65	4.43	4.75	4.70	51/74 (69%)
Primate Social Behavior (Fall 2013)	4.29	4.61	4.84	4.44	4.61	4.72	24/48 (52%)
Introduction to Biological Anthropology (Winter 2013)	4.78	4.63	4.79	4.72	4.76	4.83	59/67 (88%)
Human Behavioral Ecology (Winter 2012)	4.13	4.59	4.94	4.68	4.23	4.84	29/35 (83%)
Human Evolution (Fall 2011)	4.75	4.61	4.78	4.5	4.85	4.82	27/59 (46%)
Human Evolution (Fall 2010)	4.50	4.25	4.17	4.38	4.23	4.72	14/24 (58%)

*Median Scores: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree

Selected Qualitative Evaluations 2010–2014

Prompt “comment on the quality of instruction in this course.”

“This course was very well taught. The discussion was an incredibly effective supplement to the course. Jess was one of the best GSIs that I have had in my entire undergraduate education here at Michigan. She used our discussion very efficiently, and discussion was a very productive hour. The discussion component was very well organized with helpful powerpoints, in-class activities and discussions, and a ctools site. I really appreciated all the effort Jess put into making this discussion worthwhile, and am glad that I had the chance to work with such a great instructor”.

– Human Nutrition and Evolution (Winter 2014)

“Jess was seriously the best. She put so much effort into making materials for this class to help us learn and review difficult stuff. Her feedback on our writing pieces were very detailed and helpful. She was the GSI I’ve ever had, easily, and I’m a senior”.

– Primate Social Behavior (Fall 2013)

“Even though I did not enjoy the material of the course, I loved attending section simply because Jess' discussion section was relaxed and she was always open to questions and discussion. Jess was a very organized teacher and made sure that the class stayed on track with her carefully planned out lesson plans. She was really great at explaining concepts that seemed confusing and was always upbeat during section, which really helps to facilitate a good learning environment. She even gave us tips on how to effectively study and take exams. I loved having her as a GSI.”

– Introduction to Biological Anthropology (Winter 2013)

“Jess did a great job making sure that we all understood the course material. I liked that every week she had different activities planned out for us to do because it made the material more interesting to learn and made the students more engaged. It was clear that she spent a lot of time preparing for section and I really appreciated that. She was very helpful at explaining concepts I was confused about and she was approachable and easy to talk to.”

– Human Behavioral Ecology (Fall 2012)

“Great. Jess always knew the answers to our questions and was always willing to help. She was very organized, concise, prepared and approachable. I learned a lot in the lab, and never felt bad asking tons of questions.”

– Human Evolution (Fall 2011)

“The GSI did a great job illustrating ideas from lecture with examples and explaining confusing concepts.”

– Human Evolution (Fall 2010)

IV. Undergraduate and Graduate Mentorship

Undergraduate Mentorship

During my time at the University of Michigan I acted as a mentor to three undergraduate students. In both cases, I supervised students in the development of independent honors thesis projects with a strong bioarchaeological focus. My input ranged from assisting with the development of research questions, to discussing research design and demonstrating data collection protocols and methodology. I focused on preparing my mentees for the job market by emphasizing professional development, collaborating with these students in conference presentations and publications. In the process, the students gained analytical and professional skills that will serve them in their future careers, academic or otherwise.

- Katherine Kinkopf (Class of 2014) is currently in her fourth year of the PhD program at Berkeley, pursuing an academic career in bioarchaeology. Her honors thesis focused on a sample of burials from Middle Kerma Period Nubia, and used quantitative methodological approaches to skeletal completion to distinguish looted and unlooted burials. We co-authored a poster titled “Bioarchaeological approaches to looting: A case study from Sudan” at the 2015 Society for American Archaeology meetings in San Francisco. We submitted a co-authored paper on the same topic to the *Journal of Archaeological Science* in early October 2015.
- Polly Washabaugh (Class of 2016) wrote an honors thesis centered on the bioarchaeology of disease, specifically investigating the degree of differential social and mortuary treatment of individuals with tuberculosis in prehistoric North America. Her topic was chosen because it merges her interests in archaeology and public health, and she plans to pursue a master’s degree in Public Health at the University of Michigan after she graduates.
- Olivia Mason (Class of 2016) wrote an honors thesis focused on bioarchaeological and historical approaches to leprosy in medieval England. Her research was driven by previous excavation experience centered on leprosy cemeteries in Ireland, and she plans to pursue an academic career in bioarchaeology, applying to masters and PhD programs in fall 2016 while pursuing internship experiences working with museums collections.

I have also begun to mentor undergraduate students while conducting fieldwork, specifically during the Mortuary Archaeology of the Râmeț Bronze Age Landscape (MARBAL) project in southwest Transylvania.

- During the 2017 MARBAL season, Emilie Cobb, who had recently graduated with a BA in Anthropology from Appalachian State University, joined the team for three weeks of bioarchaeological data collection at the Muzeul Național al Unirii in Alba Iulia. Emilie took osteology and bioarchaeology courses during her undergraduate career, and this was her first bioarchaeological field experience. She participated in the collection of skeletal data, and analysis and photography of human remains and fragments. We went on to present the results of our research at the 2017 AAA meetings in Washington DC, with Emilie as first author on our poster “Health and Mortuary Treatment in Early Bronze Age Transylvania”.

- During the 2018 MARBAL field season, three Hamilton College undergraduates – Jada Langston, Lana Door and Sophia Coren – participated in four and a half weeks of excavation at the site of Ramet, where I helped to teach them archaeological field skills such as setting up the total station, taking points, laying in grid units, cutting profiles, and keeping site logs updated.

Graduate Mentorship

After receiving the Rackham Outstanding Graduate Student Instructor Award in Winter 2015 I was recruited by the Center for Research on Learning and Teaching (CRLT) to apply for one of their Graduate Teaching Consultant (GTC) positions. GTCs represent a group of experienced graduate student instructors and post-docs who work with the CRLT on activities designed to promote excellence in graduate student teaching. As a GTC, I received extensive training in consultation techniques and innovative pedagogical strategies and inclusive training practices. In this capacity I also acted as a mentor to other graduate students, observing them in the classroom, and providing them with tailored feedback, support and guidance as they refined their approach to teaching.

Since arriving at the University of Cambridge in October 2017, the biological anthropology PhD students have twice asked me to give professional development presentations. The first, on March 06, 2018, covered “Effective conference presentations and networking,” while the second, on October 17, 2018 provided an “Introduction to the US Academic Job Market”.

V. Syllabi of Previously Taught Courses

1. Introduction to Archaeology

I taught this full-semester class as instructor of record in Fall 2020 to 29 students. The course provides an introduction to archaeology and has no prerequisites. This was taught hybrid-style during the pandemic, but I incorporated (outdoor) data collection activities, small-group discussion, and pre-recorded lectures, which illustrated the basic historical, methodological, and theoretical underpinnings of the field of archaeology. Grades were based on blog post assignments, one short paper, and two exams. Assignments and activities could be scaled up to accommodate different class sizes.

2. Archaeology of Inequality

I taught this class as instructor of record in Fall 2021 to 9 students. The class is designed for both majors and non-majors. When I taught it in Fall 2022 at Harvard University it included both undergraduate and graduate students, and so it became a seminar-style class, but it could also be re-scaled as a larger introductory lecture course. The class was focused on interrogating assumptions about how inequality relates to both subsistence practices (hunting and gathering, pastoralism, agriculture), as well as forms of political organization (chiefdoms, states, empires), using an archaeological lens and case studies drawn from a wide range of regions and time periods. Grades were based on engagement and participation, three short response papers focused on readings, and a final archaeological research project that incorporated a proposal, class presentation, and paper.

3. From Artifacts to Arguments: Introduction to the Archaeology of Prehistoric Europe

This first-year writing seminar provided undergraduate students with an introduction to European prehistory and the basics of academic writing in the social sciences. Short writing assignments were scaffolded throughout the class. The class cap of 17 students provided multiple opportunities for instructor feedback and student meetings to discuss the development of their writing skills.

ANTH 130 Archaeology: Lessons from the Past

Time: T & Th, 1:30–2:45 PM
Instructor: Dr Jess Beck
Email: jessicabeck@vassar.edu
Office Hours: On Zoom,
Wednesday 10–12 & by appointment

In US popular culture, the word “archaeology” often conjures up images of buried treasure, ancient ruins, daring adventurers, and perhaps even dinosaurs¹ or aliens². In reality, the discipline of archaeology is the study of the material traces of the human past. These traces include everything from human-made objects such as pottery, stone tools, and architecture, to animal bones, plant remains, and human skeletons. Rather than seeking out individual artifacts because of their aesthetic or monetary value (*cough, cough* Indiana Jones, *cough, cough*), archaeologists excavate and analyze artifacts and remains because they provide evidence of how past people lived and how ancient societies were organized.

Archaeology is important because it allows us to access the entire scope of human history, from the Paleolithic to the present day, providing us with an understanding of what it means to be human across space and over time. This does not, however, mean that archaeology is a value-free discipline; instead, archaeological questions are shaped by history and culture. In this course, we will critically examine how archaeologists ask and answer questions about the human past, while exploring how their research is received in popular culture.

Stonehenge, England

Tourists at Stonehenge, 1875

Tourists at Stonehenge, 2016

Class Structure

All class lectures will be pre-recorded on Zoom. No live discussions or activities will be recorded. There will be two tracks for this class:

- (A) entirely remote;
- (B) hybrid remote and in-person, meeting approximately once a week for 30 minutes of discussion or activities as long as safety allows.

There will be no penalties for choosing a particular track or for switching between tracks over the course of the semester, but you need to let me know in advance for logistical reasons.

¹ Nope.

² An even bigger nope.

Learning Outcomes

By the end of this course students will be able to:

- Describe how and why archaeological sites are formed
- Explain how and why archaeological sites are and are not excavated
- Explain how archaeologists collect data in order to learn about the past
- Understand how archaeological research differs from artifact collecting
- Explain the importance of using multiple lines of evidence when studying the past
- Critically evaluate how archaeological research is received in popular culture
- Apply archaeological information to contemporary social problems

Textbook & Readings

The textbook for this course is:

Renfrew, C. & Bahn, P. (2018). *Archaeology essentials: Theory/methods/practice* (4th ed.). New York: Thames & Hudson.

The 3rd edition is also acceptable. The textbook is available through the Vassar College bookstore. All other assigned readings will be posted as pdfs on Moodle.

Grading

Your grade in this course will be based on four primary components:

Participation (20%)	Blog posts (20%)
Exams (40%)	Paper (20%)

Final course grades will be assigned using a 100-point scale. Vassar does not assign a grade of A+; an “A” grade is ≥ 95 points. A failing grade is ≤ 62 points. Grades will be rounded up or down to the nearest integer.

A- = 90–94

B+ = 87–89

B = 83–86

B- = 80–82

C+ = 77–79

C = 73–76, etc., etc.

Schedule of Exam and Paper Deadlines

Assignment	Date
Midterm Exam	Tuesday October 13–Thursday, October 15
Paper	Friday, November 20
Final Exam	TBD—Exam Period

Schedule of Blog Post Deadlines

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
Post 1	Friday, Sep 18	Friday, Sep 25	Friday, Oct 2	Friday, Oct 9
Post 2	Friday, Oct 23	Friday, Oct 30	Friday, Nov 7	Friday, Nov 12

COVID-19 NOTE: I recognize that we are living through a global pandemic and that as a result there may be points during the semester when you are unable to meet class deadlines. I am giving each of you **3 “grace days”** to use as you see fit over the course of the semester. Each grace day offers a full 24-hour extension and can be used for any assignment except the midterm and final exam. You will need to email me in advance of the assignment due date to let me know that you will be using a grace day, but you do not need to explain or justify its use.

If you use up all of your grace days and you need an extension for an emergency reason (illness, family or personal issues, etc.) please email me or visit with me during Zoom office hours; given the past six months I am inclined to be flexible. The same thing goes for absences during in-person discussion/activities or remote discussion/activities.

Grading Structure

Engagement (20%)

Engagement points will be earned by demonstrating that you are actively interacting with course material and conversations. Because of the unpredictable nature of the coming semester, engagement may be assessed in a variety of ways, ranging from written responses to worksheets and handouts, posting on online discussion boards, taking online quizzes, or conducting virtual or in-person conversations.

Whatever the format, being an engaged member of this class means that you will regularly contribute to discussion (whatever the format), including asking questions, responding to others’ questions, offering and defending your own opinions, and generally helping move the class towards new levels of understanding without dominating the discussion. Your overall course engagement will receive a single grade based on the following criteria: absent for more than five in-person classes or remote equivalents (0 pts), passive (10 pts), occasionally active (15 pts), or regularly active (20 pts). If you are having issues with accruing multiple absences for emergency reasons, please contact me to let me know—see the COVID-19 note above.

Blog posts = 20% (2 posts, 20 % each)

This course will use a WordPress blog to create a series of posts sharing what we have learned about archaeology with the rest of the world. You will need to complete one post before the midterm exam, and one post after the midterm exam, following the posting schedule for your assigned group. There are a variety of options for post format. These include:

- Audio (exactly 4 minutes)
- Video (exactly 4 minutes)
- Written text (400–500 words)

All blog posts must conform to the blog post requirements detailed in the table below. The point of the posts is to demonstrate how you can use the course content (from the assigned posting week) to understand or explain some aspect of the past or present not covered in the assigned readings or lecture material. **Students are strongly advised to work with the course assistant to refine their posts before they are published.** It is the student's responsibility to post their own contributions to the WordPress blog.

Blog post requirements
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Post title• Two images with captions• Reference list• Posts must be original work citing sources using links to or academic citations of original content (textbooks, image sources, etc).• Citations and reference lists must follow the ANTH 130 Written Assignment Formatting Guidelines.

Exams = 40% (2 exams, 20% each)

There will be a midterm and a final exam, each worth 20% of your grade. These exams will assess your understanding of lectures, course readings, and the participation component of the class. Half of the exam questions will be drawn from course readings, and half will come from lectures and the participation component of the class. The Renfrew & Bahn textbook provides study tools through the publisher's website³, and the end of each textbook chapter contains study questions. Use these tools to prepare for exam questions from these readings.

Paper = 20%

You will write one 800–1000-word paper during this class. Paper topics and assignment details will be introduced by the fourth week of class.

Papers should be submitted by email to jessicabeck@vassar.edu. They are to be submitted by midnight on the due date. For example, the paper for this class should be submitted by midnight on Friday, November 20, meaning that you will have all day Friday to work on it if you choose. Late assignments will be docked by one point for the first 24 hours, then two points per each subsequent day. See the COVID-19 Note on p.3 for information about grace days and extensions.

Office Hours

Office hours will be held on Zoom from 10:00–12:00 every Wednesday, with additional Zoom office hours scheduled by appointment for students who cannot make that time slot. To attend office hours, [please make an appointment](#) on my Google Calendar so that multiple students are not trying to meet with me simultaneously. A link to the Google Appointments page for office hours is posted on Moodle. Appointment slots will be for 20-minute increments. If you think that you will need more time to discuss a particular issue, please email me in advance.

³ <https://digital.wwnorton.com/archess4>

Plagiarism Policy

In this course you will collaborate with other students during activities and participate in group discussions where other students' ideas will not doubt affect your own. However, in your own worksheets, written assignments, and exams, do not submit someone else's words or ideas as your own. Plagiarism will result in a zero on the offending assignment and more egregious cases will incur stronger penalties in accordance with Vassar academic policy. You can read the guidelines on Integrity of Academic Work in the Vassar College Regulations available online here:

<https://deanofthecollege.vassar.edu/documents/college-regulations/VassarCollegeRegulations.pdf>

Accessibility Accommodations

If you have a condition that requires special accommodations, please have it documented by the Office for Accessibility and Educational Opportunity and provide me with a copy of your AEO accommodation letter before your accommodations are needed.

Title IX Responsibilities

All Vassar faculty members are "responsible employees;" if you inform a member of the faculty about a situation involving sexual harassment, sexual assault, relationship abuse, or stalking, they must share that information with the Title IX Coordinator. After a notification, the Title IX office will only provide outreach by email, meaning that you will control how your case will be handled—you do not have to read or reply to the email. It is entirely your decision whether or not to pursue a formal complaint.

Image Credits for First Page

1. Miqitos. Stonehenge at Dawn, Wiltshire, England [Online image]. Flickr. <https://www.flickr.com/photos/12333120@N00/3679952184>
2. Hellier, Chris. Historical Tourists at Stonehenge (2013). [Online Image] Corbis vis Getty Images. <https://www.historyextra.com/period/prehistoric/stonehenge-a-prehistoric-tourist-trap/>
3. SH Numbers (2016). [Online Image]. Heritage Action. <https://heritageaction.wordpress.com/2016/05/13/stonehenge-visitor-numbers-how-many-is-too-many/>

Image Credits for Course Topics

1. Trowel [Online image]. (2020). Pixabay. <https://pixabay.com/vectors/trowel-black-silhouette-tool-309913/>
2. Total station [Online image]. (2020). 123rf. https://www.123rf.com/clipart-vector/total_station.html?sti=m8vvgf3jux26qykczy
3. Frere, John. (1800). Handaxe. [Online image]. Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hand_axe.
4. Pine Tree [Online image] (2019). KindPNG. https://www.kindpng.com/imgv/TwRxoI_pine-tree-silhouette-transparent-background-hd-png-download/;
5. Brain [Online image]. (2019). NetClipart https://www.netclipart.com/isee/ITxot_png-transparent-images-pluspng-icon-image-brain-image/;
6. Bridge of Stones [Online image]. (2020). CashAdvance6Online <http://www.cashadvance6online.com/bridge-of-stones-wallpapers/997684069.html>
7. Pyramids [Online image]. (2020). HiClipart: <https://www.hiclipart.com/free-transparent-background-png-clipart-dfwgn>
8. Mandible traced from Buikstra, J., & Ubelaker, D. (1994). *Standards for Data Collection from Human Skeletal Remains*. Fayetteville: Arkansas Archeological Survey Research Series No. 44
9. Rabbit [Online image]. (2019). NetClipart. https://www.netclipart.com/isee/miwRbm_bunny-hopping-rabbit-jump-silhouette-gif/;
10. Mississippian jar depicting a frog [Online image] (2020). National Museum of the American Indian. <https://americanindian.si.edu/static/exhibitions/infinityofnations/woodlands/056528.html>;
11. Question mark [Online image]. (2020). PNGWING. <https://www.pngwing.com/en/free-png-zolrn>;
12. Image of unbalanced scales [Online image]. (2018). Pinclipart https://www.pinclipart.com/pindetail/TmbowT_image-of-unbalanced-scales-rule-of-law-png/
13. Books stack of three [Online image]. (2010–2020). FlatIcon https://www.flaticon.com/free-icon/books-stack-of-three_29302

COURSE SCHEDULE

* = Classes for this week will be held remotely.

Note: The readings assigned for a particular day should be read **before** that day, to ensure that you are prepared for the discussion or activities. I reserve the right to change the readings, activities, and discussion if I believe such a change is pertinent to our safety and/or the direction of the course.

Week 1. September 1 + September 3
Course overview and introduction to archaeology

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Preface + Ch. 1

Week 2. September 8 + September 10
Archaeological insights: How sites are created and discovered

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 2 + Ch. 3; Beck 2015

Week 3. September 15 + September 17
Stuff and nonsense: The archaeology of material culture

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 4 + Ch.7; Rathje & Murphy 1992
Group 1 first blog posts due Friday, September 18

Week 4. September 22 + September 24
Pathways to the past: Reconstructing the environment

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 6; Cannon & Cannon 2004; Steadman 1995
Group 2 first blog posts due Friday, September 25

Week 5. September 29 + October 1
Where is my mind? Social and cognitive archaeology

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 5 + Ch.9; The Arch & Anth Podcast Episode #143
Group 3 first blog posts due Friday, October 2

Week 6. October 6 + October 8
Explanations and ownership: The public and the past

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 10 + Ch. 11 + Ch. 12
Group 4 first blog posts due Friday, October 9

Community Care Day, Wednesday October 3

***Week 7. October 13 + October 15**
Archaeology vs. Pseudoarchaeology and Midterm Review

Readings: Parker 2016; Feder 2020

MIDTERM EXAM: October 13–October 15

Week 8. October 20 + October 22
Peopling the past: Bioarchaeology

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn Ch. 8; Overholtzer & Argueta 2017;
LaRoche & Blakey 1997; Robb 2009
Group 1 second blog posts due Friday, October 23

Week 9. October 27 + October 29
Fun with fauna: The archaeology of animals

Readings: Harris and Cipolla 2017; Morey 2006;
O'Connor 2013 (Introduction + Ch. 13); Thomas and Waterman 2013
Group 2 second blog posts due Friday, October 30

***Week 10. November 5**
Deep roots: The archaeology of plants

Readings: Fisher 2020; Twiss 2007

Community Care Day, Tuesday November 3

Group 3 second blog posts due Friday, November 7

Week 11. November 10 + November 12
Archaeology today: Modern problems, ancient solutions?

Readings: Crabtree et al. 2017; De León 2012; Groesbek et al. 2014; Lentz et al. 2018
Group 4 second blog posts due Friday, November 12

Week 12. November 17 + November 19
The Archaeology of Native North America & Thanksgiving

Readings: Bugos 2019; Leonard et al. 2020; Schilling 2012; Timmerman 2020
Friday, November 20 ANTH-130 paper due

THANKSGIVING BREAK
Saturday November 21–Sunday November 29

***Week 13. December 1 + December 3**
The archaeology of inequality; the inequality of archaeology

Readings: Beck 2020; *Additional reading/podcast TBD*;
Moser 2007; White and Draycott 2020

***Week 14. December 8**
Review for final exam

Remote review for final exam

STUDY PERIOD: Thursday, December 10–Sunday, December 13

READING LIST

- Beck, J. (2015, February 27) How do archaeologists find sites? *Bone Broke*.
<https://bonebroke.org/2015/02/27/how-do-archaeologists-find-sites/>
- Beck, J. (2020). The human position: The potential of bioarchaeology for studies of inequality in Iberian Late Prehistory. In K. Lillios and P. Díaz-del-Río (Eds.), *Political matters in prehistory: Papers in honor of Antonio Gilman Guillén*. Bibliotheca Praehistorica Hispana.
- Bugos, C. (2019, November 26). The Myths of the Thanksgiving story and the lasting damage they imbue. *Smithsonian Magazine*. <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/thanksgiving-myth-and-what-we-should-be-teaching-kids-180973655/>
- Cannon, K. P., & Boeka Cannon, M. (2004). Zooarchaeology and wildlife management in the greater Yellowstone ecosystem. In R. L. Lyman & K. Cannon (Eds.), *Zooarchaeology and conservation biology* (pp. 45–60). Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press.
- Crabtree, S. A., Vaughn, L. J. S., & Crabtree, N. T. (2017). Reconstructing Ancestral Pueblo food webs in the southwestern United States. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 81, 116–127.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2017.03.005>
- De León, J. (2012). “Better to be hot than caught”: Excavating the conflicting roles of migrant material culture. *American Anthropologist*, 114(3), 477–495. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1548-1433.2012.01447.x>
- Feder, K. L. (2020). Prehistoric E.T. The fantasy of ancient astronauts. In *Frauds, myths, and mysteries: Science and pseudoscience in archaeology* (10th ed., pp. 196–219). New York: Oxford University Press.
- Fisher, C. (2020). Archaeology for sustainable agriculture. In *Journal of Archaeological Research* (Vol. 28). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-019-09138-5>
- Groesbeck, A. S., Rowell, K., Lepofsky, D., & Salomon, A. K. (2014). Ancient clam gardens increased shellfish production: Adaptive strategies from the past can inform food security today. *PLoS ONE*, 9(3). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0091235>
- Harris, O. J. T., & Cipolla, C. (2017). Multi-species archaeology: People, plants and animals. In *Archaeological theory in the new millennium: Introducing current perspectives* (pp. 152–170). Basingstoke: Taylor & Francis.
- LaRoche, C. J., & Blakey, M. L. (1997). Seizing intellectual power: The dialogue at the New York African Burial Ground. *Historical Archaeology*, 31(3), 84–106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf03374233>
- Lentz, D. L., Dunning, N. P., Scarborough, V. L., & Grazioso, L. (2018). Imperial resource management at the ancient Maya city of Tikal: A resilience model of sustainability and collapse. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 52(August), 113–122.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2018.08.005>
- Leonard, L., Moss, J., Khan, A., & Knuckles, F. (2020, February 20). As College works to comply with NAGPRA, community interrogates institutional, academic history. *The Miscellany News*.
<https://miscellanynews.org/2020/02/20/news/vassar-stores-native-american-human-remains-violates-nagpra/>
- Morey, D. F. (2006). Burying key evidence: The social bond between dogs and people. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 33(2), 158–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2005.07.009>

- Moser, S. (2007). On disciplinary culture: Archaeology as fieldwork and its gendered associations. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory*, 14(3), 235–263. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-007-9033-5>
- O'Connor, T. (2013). Introduction. In *The archaeology of animal bones* (pp. 1–4). Thrupp: Sutton Publishing.
- O'Connor, T. (2013). Settling down: The domestication of animals and people. In *The archaeology of animal bones* (pp. 147–159). Thrupp: Sutton Publishing.
- Overholtzer, L., & Argueta, J. R. (2018). Letting skeletons out of the closet: the ethics of displaying ancient Mexican human remains. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 24(5), 508–530. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527258.2017.1390486>
- Parker, E. A. (2016). The proliferation of pseudoarchaeology through “reality” television programming. In J. J. Card & D. S. Anderson (Eds.), *Lost city, found pyramid: Understanding alternative archaeologies and pseudoscientific practices* (pp. 149–166). Tuscaloosa: The University of Alabama Press.
- Rathje, W. L. & Murphy, C. (1992). Garbage and History In *Rubbish! The archaeology of garbage*. (pp. 30–52). Tuscon: University of Arizona Press.
- Rivera, M. (Producer) (2020, June 24). The Arch & Anth Podcast. Episode 143: How do experts discover and study rock art in Southeast Asia? Interview with Noel Hidalgo Tan. [Audio podcast]. <https://archandanth.com/episode-143-interview-with-noel-hidalgo-tan/>
- Robb, J. (2009). Towards a critical Ötziography: Inventing prehistoric bodies. In H. Lambert & M. McDonald (Eds.), *Social bodies* (pp. 100–128). New York: Berghan Books.
- Schilling, T. (2012). Building Monks Mound, Cahokia, Illinois, A.D. 800-1400. *Journal of Field Archaeology*, 37(4), 302–313. <https://doi.org/10.1179/0093469012Z.00000000027>
- Steadman, D. W. (1995). Prehistoric extinctions of Pacific island birds: Biodiversity meets zooarchaeology. *Science*, 267(5201), 1123–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.267.5201.1123>
- Thomas, J. T., & Waterman, A. J. (2013). Down the rabbit hole: the significance of Late Neolithic lagomorph figurines in anthropological perspective. *Archaeological Review from Cambridge*, 28(2), 113–131.
- Timmerman, N. A. (2020). Contested indigenous landscapes: Indian mounds and the political creation of the mythical “mound builder” race. *Ethnohistory*, 67(1), 75–95. <https://doi.org/10.1215/00141801-7888741>
- Twiss, K. C. (2020). Identity: Food, affiliation, and distinction. In *The archaeology of food: Identity, politics, and ideology in the prehistoric and historic past* (pp. 129–154). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- White, W., & Draycott, C. (2020, July 7). Why the whiteness of archaeology is a problem. *Sapiens*. <https://www.sapiens.org/archaeology/archaeology-diversity/>

ANTHRO 1033: Archaeology of Inequality

Location: Peabody 561
Meeting Times: TR 1:30–2:45
Instructor: Dr Jess Beck
Email: jbeck1@fas.harvard.edu
Office Hours: Th, 3:00–4:00 or by appointment on Zoom.

In 2018, Oxfam reported that the 26 richest people on the planet had the same net worth as half of the global population.⁴ The rampant wealth disparities in the modern world lead us to ask whether inequality is an inescapable component of all societies. Through its unique access to the deep time of human prehistory, archaeology allows us to question myths and just-so stories about the origins and inevitability of inequality. In this course, we will examine how different ways of making a living, from food procurement to economic and political organization, have worked to either amplify or diminish inequalities in human communities. This course will cover topics that resonate in the past and present: How do elites justify their monopolization of power and resources? Are there alternatives to hierarchy in large-scale communities? What strategies have past people used to evade the inequitable demands of states and empires? This course will explore how archaeologists draw upon multiple lines of evidence—including material culture, architecture, and the remains of ancient plants, animals, and people—to develop a holistic understanding of inequality in past societies.

Learning Outcomes

- Explain the importance of using multiple lines of evidence to draw conclusions about the past
- Learn about the diversity of ways that past people have structured their communities
- Develop an understanding of human social flexibility at a variety of time scales
- Critically evaluate whether inequality is an inevitable component of human social systems

Class Structure

Though this is a lecture-based class, it will also incorporate activities, small group discussion, and large group discussion.

Readings

There is no assigned textbook for this course. PDFs of all assigned readings will be provided on Canvas.

Grading

Your grade will be based on five components:

Engagement	Response Paper 1	Response Paper 2	Response Paper 3	Final Research Paper & Presentation
20%	15%	15%	15%	35%

⁴ See [this](#) Vox article for a thoughtful breakdown of how that calculation was achieved.

Plagiarism Policy

In this course, you will collaborate with other students during activities and participate in group discussions where other students' ideas will not doubt affect your own. However, in your own assignments, presentations, and papers, do not submit someone else's words or ideas as your own. Plagiarism will result in a zero on the offending assignment and more egregious cases will incur stronger penalties in accordance with Harvard academic policy. You can read the guidelines on the Harvard College handbook for students here:

<https://handbook.fas.harvard.edu/book/academic-integrity>

COVID-19 NOTE: I recognize that we are living through a global pandemic and that as a result there may be points during the semester when you are unable to meet class deadlines. I am giving each of you 2 "grace days" to use as you see fit over the course of the semester. Each grace day offers a full 24-hour extension and can be used for any assignment except the final research presentation. You will need to email me in advance of the assignment due date to let me know that you will be using a grace day, but you do not need to explain or justify its use. **If you use up all of your grace days and you need an extension for an emergency reason (illness, family or personal issues, etc.) please email me or visit me during office hours;** given the events of the past year and a half I am inclined to be flexible. The same thing goes for absences during in-person discussion/activities or remote discussion/activities.

Grading Structure

Note: All formal written assignments for this course should conform to the Written Assignments Guidelines distributed on the first day of class and available on the class website.

Engagement (20%): Whatever the format, being an engaged member of this class means that you will regularly contribute to discussion, including asking questions, responding to others' questions, offering and defending your own opinions, and generally helping move the class towards new levels of understanding without dominating the discussion. Your overall course engagement will receive a single grade based on the following criteria: absent for more than five in-person classes or remote equivalents (0 pts), passive (10 pts), occasionally active (15 pts), or regularly active (20 pts). If you are having issues with accruing multiple absences for emergency reasons, please contact me to let me know—see the COVID-19 note above.

Short Response Papers (15% each): Each paper will ask you to respond to a prompt that addresses a major issue pertaining to one course unit. These short response papers will be between 1000–1200 words. You will not be required to do additional outside reading; instead, you will be asked to critically evaluate and synthesize concepts and evidence drawn from readings, lectures, and activities. Prompts will be provided ≥ 1 week in advance of due dates.

Final Research Presentation (5%): Your final research presentation will occur during the last week of class. During your presentation you will share an overview of your final research paper with the class. Guidelines for your final research presentation will be distributed by Week 10.

Final Research Paper (30%): The research paper provides you with an opportunity to explore some aspect of inequality in the human past in greater depth. If there is a period, region, or dimension of inequality that has always fascinated you, this is your chance to learn more

about it through engaging with the archaeological literature. Detailed guidelines for the final research paper will be presented by Week 7. You will submit a short research paper proposal to Dr Beck by Week 11.

Papers should be submitted by email to jbeck1@fas.harvard.edu. They are to be submitted by midnight on the due date. For example, the first short paper for this class should be submitted by midnight on Friday, October 1, meaning that you will have all day Friday to work on it if you choose. Late assignments will be docked by one point for the first 24 hours, then two points per each subsequent day. See the COVID-19 Note on p.2 for information about grace days and extensions.

ASSIGNMENT DUE DATES

Assignment (% Final Grade)	Due Date
Short Response Paper 1 (15%)	Friday, October 1
Short Response Paper 2 (15%)	Friday, October 29
Research Paper Proposal (5%)	Wednesday, November 10
Short Response Paper 3 (15%)	Wednesday, November 23
Final Research Presentation (5%)	Tuesday, November 30*
Final Research Paper (25%)	Thursday, December 2

*Depending on class enrolment, final research presentations may extend to Thursday, December 2nd if scheduling requires.

Class Schedule and Reading List

Note: The readings should be read before the day on which they are listed to ensure that you are prepared for the lecture, discussion, and activities. I reserve the right to change the readings if I feel it is pertinent to the direction of the course; readings would be exchanged rather than added.

Week 1: Introduction

Thursday, September 2

Topic: Introduction to course

Readings: Graeber & Wengrow 2018

UNIT I: Tipping the Scales

Week 2: What is inequality & how can archaeologists assess it?

Tuesday, September 7

Topic: What is inequality?

Readings: Afonso, Lafleur & Alarcón 2015; Kohler et al. 2017

Optional Reading: Krieger & Davey Smith 2004

Thursday, September 9

Topic: Introduction to archaeological approaches

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn 2018, Chapter 2

Activity: *Material traces of inequality*

Week 3: Measuring Inequality

Tuesday, September 14

Topic: Analyzing inequality data

Readings: No readings—fill out and submit your assignment in preparation for this class.

Thursday, September 16

Topic: How have past scholars thought about inequality and human social change?

Readings: Trigger 2008

Week 4: Hunting and gathering

Tuesday, September 21

Topic: Hunting and gathering

Readings: Kelly 1995 Preface & Chapter 1; Lee 1979 excerpt

Thursday, September 23

Topic: Scale, complexity, and inequality in hunter-gatherer groups

Readings: Dietrich et al., 2012; Ortmann & Kidder 2012

Week 5: Horticulture and pastoralism

Tuesday, September 28

Topic: Coalition and consensus in hunter-gatherer and forager-farmer societies + discussion of written assignment guidelines

Readings: Angelbeck 2016; Henry & Barrier 2016

UNIT II: Scaling up?

Thursday, September 30

Topic: On the hoof—introduction to pastoralism

Readings: McCabe 1990

Week 6: Pastoralism and agriculture

Tuesday, October 5

Topic: Pastoralism and inequality

Readings: Wright 2013; Arbuckle 2012

Thursday, October 7

Topic: Subsistence transitions

Readings: Diamond 1987; Antrosio 2011; Wyman 2020 (podcast)

Week 7: Emerging inequalities

Tuesday, October 12

Topic: Farmers in flux

Readings: Price 1995; Wright 2014

Thursday, October 14

Topic: Production, inheritance, and inequality + final research paper guidelines

Readings: Alden Smith et al. 2010

Week 8: Early complex societies and elites

Tuesday, October 19

Topic: Introduction to early complex societies

Readings: Gilman 1981

Activity: *Decision-making and scalar stress*

Thursday, October 21

Topic: Commodity and control: political-economic approaches to power

Readings: Earle et al. 2015

Guest: *Dr Colin Quinn (Hamilton College)*

Week 9: Are elites optional?

Tuesday, October 26

Topic: Elites make the world go round

Readings: Beck 2006; Earle & Spriggs 2015

Thursday, October 28

Topic: Copper Age Iberia: Aggregations and monumentality without elites

Readings: Beck 2020

UNIT III: The familiar

Week 10: Introducing states and empires

Tuesday, November 2

Topic: Introducing states + final presentation guidelines
Readings: Green 2020; Wyman 2021 (podcast)

Thursday, November 4

Topic: Introducing empires
Readings: Sinopoli 2001

Week 11: Power and control

Tuesday, November 9

Topic: Labor, infrastructure & inequality
Readings: Becker 2020; Wilkinson 2019

Thursday, November 11

Topic: Imperial power
Readings: Morrison and Lycett 1994
Activity: *Campus-based activity*

Week 12: Partitioning power and evading the state

Tuesday, November 16

Topic: Partitioning power
Readings: Fargher et al. 2010; Green 2021
Guest: *Dr Adam Green (University of Cambridge)*

Thursday, November 18

Topic: Evading the state: shatter zones and peripheries
Readings: Galaty 2013; Raffield 2021

Week 13: Are there alternatives?

Tuesday, November 23

Topic: Human flexibility write large
Readings: Scott 2010 (short video); Wengrow & Graeber 2015

Thursday, November 25

Topic: Essential tensions: inequality and alternatives
Readings: Borck 2018, Quinn & Beck 2016

NOVEMBER 25–29 THANKSGIVING BREAK

Week 14: Conclusions and student presentations

Tuesday, November 30

Topic: Student Presentations
Readings: None

Thursday, December 2

Topic: Class conclusions
Readings: None

Reading List

- Afonso, H., LaFleur, M. & Alarcón, D. (2015). Concepts of inequality. *Development Issues*, 1, 1-2. <https://www.un.org/development/desa/dpad/publication/no-1-concepts-of-inequality/>
- Alden Smith, E., Borgerhoff Mulder, M., Bowles, S., Gurven, M., Hertz, T., & Shenk, M. (2010). Production systems, inheritance and inequality in premodern societies: Conclusions. *Current Anthropology*, 51(1), 85-94. <https://doi.org/10.1086/649029>
- Angelbeck, B. (2016). The balance of autonomy and alliance in anarchic societies: the organization of defences in the Coast Salish past. *World Archaeology*, 48(1), 51-69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00438243.2015.1131620>
- Antrosio, J. (2011, June 1). *Agriculture: Jared Diamond's worst mistake?* Living Anthropologically. <https://www.livinganthropologically.com/archaeology/agriculture-worst-mistake/>
- Arbuckle, B. S. (2012). Pastoralism, provisioning, and power at Bronze Age Achemhöük, Turkey. *American Anthropologist*, 114(3), 462-476. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1548-1433.2012.01446.x>
- Beck, J. (2020). The labor of building a community: Exploring the divergent trajectories of complex sites in Copper Age Iberia. *American Anthropologist*, 122(4), 896-901. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.13498>
- Beck Jr., R. A. (2006). Persuasive politics and domination at Moundville and Cahokia. In B. M. Butler & P. D. Welch (Eds.), *Leadership and Polity in Mississippian Society* (pp. 19-42). Southern Illinois University at Carbondale Center for Archaeological Investigations, Occasional Paper no. 33.
- Becker, S. K. (2020). Why heterarchy? A view from the Tiwanaku state's (AD 500–1100) labor force. *American Anthropologist*, 122(4), 934–939. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.13499>
- Borck, L. (2018). Constructing the future history: Prefiguration as historical epistemology and the chronopolitics of archaeology. *Journal of Contemporary Archaeology*, 5(2), 229-238. <https://doi.org/10.1558/jca.33560>
- Diamond, J. (1987). The worst mistake in the history of the human race. *Discover*, 91-93.
- Dietrich, O., Heun, M., Notroff, J., Schmidt, K. & Zarnkow, M. (2012). The role of cult and feasting in the emergence of Neolithic communities. New evidence from Göbekli Tepe, south-eastern Turkey. *Antiquity*, 86(333), 674-695. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00047840>
- Earle, T., Ling, J., Uhnér, C., Stos-Gale, Z., & Melheim, L. (2015). The political economy and metal trade in Bronze Age Europe: Understanding regional variability in terms of comparative advantages and articulations. *European Journal of Archaeology*, 18(4), 633-657. <https://doi.org/10.1179/1461957115y.0000000008>
- Earle, T. & Spriggs, M. (2015). Political economy in prehistory: A Marxist approach to Pacific sequences. *Current Anthropology*, 56(4): 515–544. <https://doi.org/10.1086/682284>
- Fargher, L., Blanton, R., & Heredia Espinoza, V. (2010) Egalitarian ideology and political power in prehispanic Central Mexico: The case of Tlaxcallan. *Latin American Antiquity*, 21(3): 227-251. <https://doi.org/10.7183/1045-6635.21.3.227>

- Galaty, M. L. (2013). "An offense to honor is never forgiven . . .": Violence and landscape archaeology in highland northern Albania. In S. Ralph (Ed.), *The Archaeology of Violence: Interdisciplinary Approaches* (pp. 143-157). State University of New York Press.
- Gilman, A. (1981). The development of social stratification in Bronze Age Europe. *Current Anthropology*, 22(1): 1-23. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/2742414>
- Graeber, D., & Wengrow, D. (2018). How to change the course of human history. *Eurozine*. <https://www.eurozine.com/change-course-human-history/>
- Green, A. (2020). Debt and inequality: Comparing the "means of specification" in the early cities of Mesopotamia and the Indus civilization. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 60, 101232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2020.101232>
- Green, A. (2021). Killing the priest-king: Addressing egalitarianism in the Indus civilization. *Journal of Archaeological Research*, 29, 153-202. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-020-09147-9>
- Henry, E. R., & Barrier, C. R. (2016). The organization of dissonance in Adena-Hopewell societies of eastern North America. *World Archaeology*, 48(1),87-109. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00438243.2015.1132175>
- Kelly, R. L. (2013). Hunter-gatherers and anthropology. In *The Lifeways of Hunter-Gatherers: The Foraging Spectrum*, (2nd ed., pp. 1-37). Cambridge University Press.
- Kohler, T., Smith, M. E., Bogaard, A., Feinman, G. M., Peterson, C. E., Betzenhauser, A., Pailes, M., Stone, E. C., Prentiss A., Dennehy, T. J., Ellyson, L. J., Nicholas, L. M., Faulseit, R. K., Styring, A., Whitlam, J., Fochesato, M., Foor, T. A., & Bowles, S. (2017). Greater post-Neolithic wealth disparities in Eurasia than in North America and Mesoamerica. *Nature*, 551, 619-622. <https://doi:10.1038/nature24646>
- Krieger, N., & Davey Smith, G. (2004). "Bodies count," and body counts: Social epidemiology and embodying inequality. *Epidemiologic Reviews*, 26, 92-103. <https://doi.org/10.1093/epirev/mxh009>
- Lee, R. B. (1979). Hunting as a life's work + hunting success and status differences, In *The !Kung San: Men, Women, and Work in a Foraging Society* (pp. 242–249). Cambridge University Press.
- McCabe, J. T. (1990). Turkana pastoralism: A case against the tragedy of the commons. *Human Ecology*, 18(1), 81-103. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4602953>
- Morrison, K., & Lycett, M. (1994). Centralized power, centralized authority? Ideological claims and archaeological patterns. *Asian Perspectives*, 33(2), 327-350. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/42928325>
- Ortmann, A. L., & Kidder, T. R. (2012). Building Mound A at Poverty Point, Louisiana: Monumental public architecture, ritual practice, and implications for hunter-gatherer complexity. *Geoarchaeology*, 28, 66-86. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gea.21430>
- Quinn, C., & Beck, J. (2016). Essential tensions: A framework for exploring inequality through mortuary archaeology and bioarchaeology. *Open Archaeology* 2: 18-41. <https://doi.org/10.1515/opar-2016-0002>
- Raffield, B. (2021). Broken worlds: Towards an archaeology of the shatter zone. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-021-09520-y>

- Renfrew, C., & Bahn, P. (2018). What is left? The variety of the evidence. In *Archaeology Essentials: Theory/Methods/Practice*. (4th ed., pp.38-61). Thames & Hudson.
- Scott, J. (2010, November 4). *The art of not being governed* [Video]. The MacMillan Report, Yale University. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aVwrUsib4vU>
- Sinopoli C.M. (2001). Empires. In G.M.Feinman & T.D. Price (Eds.), *Archaeology at the Millennium* (pp.439–471), Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-72611-3_13
- Trigger, B. G. (2008). Evolutionary archaeology. In *A History of Archaeological Thought*. (2nd Ed., pp.166-210). Cambridge University Press.
- Wilkinson, D. (2020). Infrastructure and inequality: An archaeology of the Inka road through the Amaybamba cloud forests. *Journal of Social Archaeology*, 19(1), 27-46. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469605318822551>
- Wengrow, D., & Graeber, D. (2015). Farewell to the “childhood of man”: Ritual, seasonality, and the origins of inequality. *Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute*, 21(3), 597-619. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9655.12247>
- Wright, J. (2013). Inequality on the surface: Horses, power, and community in the Mongolian Bronze Age. In B. Arbuckle & S. McCart (Eds.), *Animals and Inequality in the Ancient World* (pp. 275-293). University Press of Colorado. <https://doi.org/10.5876/9781607322863.c013>
- Wright, K.I. (2014). Domestication and inequality? Households, corporate groups and food processing tools at Neolithic Çatalhöyük. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 33, 1–33. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2013.09.007>
- Wyman, P. (Host). (2020, September 10). The first farmers [Audio podcast episode]. In *Tides of History*. Wondery. <https://wondery.com/shows/tides-of-history/episode/5629-the-first-farmers/>
- Wyman, P. (Host). (2021, July 29). Cities, states, and living in ancient Mesopotamia [Audio podcast episode]. In *Tides of History*. Wondery. <https://wondery.com/shows/tides-of-history/episode/5629-cities-states-and-living-in-ancient-mesopotamia/>

ANTH-170-52: From Artifacts to Arguments: Introduction to the Archaeology of Prehistoric Europe

Time: MW: 12:00–1:15

Location: BH 101

Email: jessicabeck@vassar.edu

Office Hours: M: 2:00–4:00
BH 312

How did humans survive during the last Ice Age? Who is responsible for the cave paintings of Lascaux? What exactly is a henge? In this course, we will explore the answers to these questions and more, covering topics ranging from ancient subsistence systems to exchange networks, mortuary practices, and technology.

The class is divided into four units: (1) Introduction to Archaeological Theory and History; (2) The Paleolithic; (3) The Neolithic; (4) The Copper Age–Bronze Age. Students will learn to evaluate archaeological evidence, assess the importance of theory in reconstructing prehistoric lifeways, and identify key sites, archaeologists, and artifacts in European prehistory. In addition to painting a portrait of the economies, exchange networks, social organization and ritual practices of early European communities, this course also emphasizes the utility of different archaeological lines of evidence, describing the complementary information that can be recovered from lithics, ceramics, animal bones, human bones and ancient plant remains.

Over the course of the seminar, students will learn how to formulate clear arguments, draw upon scientific evidence, and develop strategies for writing and revising research papers. Class time will also be devoted to developing key writing and research skills, such as structuring academic papers, identifying appropriate sources, interpreting and responding to feedback.

Learning Outcomes

First-Year Writing Seminar (from the VCWC)

- **Formulating an Argument:** Participate in a scholarly conversation by crafting a paper with a clear, well-organized argument and establishing its relevance to the intended audience.
- **Marshalling Evidence:** Identify, evaluate, and accurately represent an understanding of primary and secondary source materials (g. summary, paraphrase, quotation) and show the relevance of those materials to their own arguments.

- **Writing as Process:** Engage various strategies for using writing to analyze and develop their ideas (free-writing, idea-mapping, reverse-outlining, revising, etc.).
- **Academic Integrity:** Distinguish between plagiarism and the responsible use of sources and cite according to disciplinary conventions.
- **Mechanics and Usage:** Formulate their ideas in clear and cogent prose while adhering to rules of grammatical correctness

ANTH-170-05

- Explain how archaeologists collect data in order to learn about people in the past.
- Compare the similarities and differences between life in the prehistoric past and life in the present.
- Critically evaluate how archaeological research is received in the media and popular culture.
- Formulate an archaeological research question and review multiple lines of academic evidence in order to answer the question.

Readings

All assigned readings will be posted as pdfs on Moodle.

Grading

Your grade will be based on four components:

Attendance and participation (30%)	Quizzes (10 %)
Short writing assignments (30%)	Final Research Paper and Presentation (30%)

Grading Structure

Attendance and participation (30%): Every week an attendance sheet will circulate that you are required to sign. It is your responsibility to sign the attendance sheet. If you are not able to do so at the beginning of class, you are responsible for asking for the attendance sheet at the end of class. Full attendance for all 26 sessions of the course will guarantee 15% of this attendance grade. You are allowed one unexcused absence which will not alter your final grade. If you have already missed one class and need to miss another class for emergency reasons, please email me or let me know

However, simply showing up to class is not sufficient to achieve the full 30%. Focused participation in labs or activities, and active participation in group discussions will comprise the remaining 15% of this mark. You will also need to schedule one individual conference with Dr. Beck during Weeks 8 and 9 (Monday, March 23–Friday, April 3) in order to discuss your final paper topic. This will count towards your participation grade.

Short Writing Assignments (30%): This course will incorporate three short writing assignments that are 3–5 pages in length. Short Writing Assignment 1 will be divided into a draft and a final, with each component worth 5%. Short Writing Assignments 2 and 3 will each be worth 10% of your final grade.

Quizzes (10%): There will be five quizzes over the course of the semester. Quizzes will take between 10–15 minutes of time at the beginning of class. These will cover material learned during the preceding sections of class and will vary in format, including multiple choice, short answer, and identification questions.

Final Research Paper (30%): The final research paper will have both a written and a presentation component. The written component consists of a short 1–2 pp. project proposal that will be used to develop an 8–10 pp. research paper that focuses on an archaeological topic of your choice and cites appropriate academic sources. Your topic must be drawn from one of the main categories that will be presented to you during the fifth week of class. You will need to choose a specific project topic and submit your project proposal by Monday, March 23 (the first class after spring break), which will be worth 5% of your grade. Your final paper will be worth 20% of your final grade. It should draw from and properly cite peer-reviewed books and articles, using data outlined in these sources to present a central argument and critically evaluate the research that has been conducted on the topic thus far. During the final week of class, you will prepare a short presentation that summarizes your research for your peers. This final project presentation will be worth 5% of the final grade.

Writing assignments will be submitted by email to jessicabeck@vassar.edu. They are to be submitted by midnight on the due date. For example, the draft of SWA1 must be submitted by midnight on Wednesday, February 12, meaning that you will have all day on February 12 to work on it if you choose. Late assignments will be docked by two points per day.

Plagiarism Policy

In this course you will collaborate with other students during activities and participate in group discussions where other students' ideas will not doubt affect your own. However, in your own worksheets, written assignments, and final presentations, do not submit someone else's words or ideas as your own. Plagiarism will result in a zero on the offending assignment and more egregious cases will incur stronger penalties in accordance with Vassar academic policy. You can read the guidelines on Integrity of Academic Work in the Vassar College Regulations available online here:

<https://deanofthecollege.vassar.edu/documents/college-regulations/VassarCollegeRegulations.pdf>

Vassar College Writing Center

You are encouraged to visit the VCWC at least once over the course of this class in order to receive feedback and advice on your FWS writing assignments.

“The Writing Center provides all Vassar students with a community of experienced peer-readers and writers by offering free, one-to-one consultations at any stage of the writing process—from generating a thesis and structuring an argument to fine-tuning a draft. All students are invited to bring writing projects to the Center, including academic essays from any disciplines, lab reports, creative writing, senior theses, and fellowship statements, as well as resumes, cover letters, and CVs. Students can also bring speaking assignments, including oral and multimedia presentations, poster talks, and teaching plans for leading class discussion.”

More information: <https://ltrc.vassar.edu/writing-center/>

Hours: Sundays-Thursdays: 3:00-11:00pm

Appointments: Make appointments online at <https://vassar.mywconline.com/>

Location: Thompson Memorial Library (Main Library) in Room 122

Artifacts to Arguments: Deadlines for Writing Assignments and Presentations

Date	Assignment	Length	% Grade
Wednesday, 12 Feb.	Short Writing Assignment 1: Draft	3–5 pp.	5%
Wednesday, 04 March	Short Writing Assignment 1: Final	3–5 pp.	5%
Monday, 23 March	Final Research Paper Proposal	1–2 pp.	5%
Wednesday, 01 April	Short Writing Assignment 2	3–5 pp.	10%
Wednesday, 22 April	Short Writing Assignment 3	3–5 pp.	10%
MW, 04–06 May	Final Research Paper Presentations		5%
Wednesday, 06 May	Final Research Paper	8–10 pp.	20%

Please note that during Week 8–9 (23 March–03 April 2020), you must schedule an individual conference with Dr. Beck.

Artifacts to Arguments: Quiz Dates

Date	Quiz	Topic
Monday, 03 February	1	Map of Europe
Monday, 17 February	2	Archaeology & The History of Archaeology in Europe
Monday, 02 March	3	The Paleolithic
Monday, 06 April	4	The Neolithic
Monday, 20 April	5	Mortuary & Bioarchaeology + the Copper Age/EBA

COURSE SCHEDULE

Note: The readings assigned for a particular day should be read **before** that day, to ensure that you are prepared for the lecture, discussion, and activities. I reserve the right to change the readings if I feel it is pertinent to the direction of the course, though in this event readings would be exchanged, rather than added.

Week 1: Introduction

Wednesday, January 22

- **Lecture:** Introduction to course, instructor, and syllabus
- **Activity:** Mapping it out: How well do you know European geography?

Week 2: From artifacts to arguments: Introduction to archaeology

Monday, January 27: What is archaeology?

- **Reading:** Renfrew and Bahn 2018, Chapter 1.

Wednesday, January 29: How do archaeologists make claims about the past?

- **Reading:** Ashmore and Sharer, Ch. 8
- **Review:** Map of Europe

Week 3: Writing Workshop I + Early prehistorians and their impact

Monday, February 3: What Archaeologists Study + Writing Workshop I

- **Reading:** Edwards et al., 2016; Graff and Berkenstein 2006; Lieberman 2019
- **Quiz 1:** Map of Europe

Wednesday, February 5: The history of European prehistory

- **Reading:** Trigger 2006, Chapter 4

Week 4: Who *are* these guys? Neandertals and early “modern” humans

Monday, February 10: Who were the Neanderthals?

- **Reading:** Bahn 1998; Stringer and Davies 2001
- **Video:** Neanderthal (PBS)

Wednesday, February 12: Apples and oranges? Comparing Neanderthals and humans

- **Reading:** Speth 2004

SHORT WRITING ASSIGNMENT 1 DRAFT DUE

Week 5: A hard rock life: Paleolithic material culture

Monday, February 17: What can we learn from lithics?

- **Reading:** Ambrose 2001
- **Quiz 2:** Archaeology & the history of archaeology in Europe
- **Activity:** Flint knapping demonstration

Wednesday, February 19: Paleolithic material culture

- Presentation of topics for Final Research Paper
- **Reading:** Price 2013, Chapter 3 (pp. 56–76; 118–122)

Week 6: You are what you eat: Subsistence in the Paleolithic

Monday, February 24: How do archaeologists reconstruct ancient diets?

- **Reading:** Hastorf 2016, Preface and Chapter 4 (pp. 83-107)

Wednesday, February 27: Hunting and gathering in the Paleolithic

- **Reading:** Grayson & Delpech 2002
- **Activity:** Breaking down a complex academic article
- **Video:** Debunking the Paleo Diet—Christina Warinner

Week 7: Putting down roots: The agricultural revolution

Monday, March 2: The domestication of plants

- **Reading:** Diamond 1987; Larsen 2006
- **Quiz 3:** The Paleolithic
- **Activity:** The Modern Diet

Wednesday, March 4. The domestication of animals

- **Reading:** Redding 2005
- **Activity:** Identifying animal bones
- **Mid-semester feedback distributed**

SHORT WRITING ASSIGNMENT 1 FINAL DUE

SPRING BREAK March 6 – March 22

Week 8: Settling down: Writing Workshop II + Early villages in Europe

Monday March 23: Writing Workshop II

- **Reading:** Savage & Yeh 2019

FINAL RESEARCH PAPER PROPOSAL DUE

Wednesday, March 25: Early villages

- **Reading:** Bogaard et al. 2009

Week 9: Voting with your feet: Neolithic material culture and prehistoric migrations

Monday, March 30: What ceramics can teach us about past cultures

- **Reading:** Holtorf 2002; Loubser 2003
- **Activity:** Collecting data from ceramics

Wednesday, April 01: Prehistoric mobility & migrations in Europe

- **Reading:** Vander Linden 2016

SHORT WRITING ASSIGNMENT 2 DUE

Week 10: Rock & roll: Late prehistoric mortuary practices

Monday April 6: Bioarchaeology: Reconstructing the past using human skeletal remains

- **Reading:** Meyer et al. 2009
- **Quiz 4:** The Neolithic

Wednesday April 8: “The dead don’t bury themselves”

- **Reading:** Parker Pearson 2000, Chapter 6
- **Activity:** Analyzing Mortuary Practices

Week 11: Archaeology & the media + navigating library sources

Monday, April 13: Archaeology and the media

- **Reading:** Finn 2001; Rocks-MacQueen 2014
- **Activity:** Navigating library resources.

Wednesday April 15

- **NO CLASS. RESEARCH DAY FOR FINAL PAPERS.**

Week 12: Pretty metal: The Copper Age & Early Bronze Age

Monday, April 20: Europe during the third millennium BCE

- **Reading:** TBD

Wednesday, April 22: Case Study: The Iberian Copper Age

- **Reading:** Garcia Sanjuán et al. 2013

SHORT WRITING ASSIGNMENT 3 DUE

Week 13: Mean girls? Status and society during the Bronze Age

Monday, April 27: Hierarchy, territoriality and power during the Bronze Age

- **Reading:** Price 2013, Chapter 5
- **Quiz 5:** Mortuary archaeology, bioarchaeology, and the Copper Age

Wednesday, April 29: Case study: The Romanian Early Bronze Age

- **Reading:** Earle et al. 2015

Week 14: Student Presentations and CEQs

Monday, May 4

- Student Presentations, Round I
- CEQs

FINAL RESEARCH PAPER DUE

Image credits: Löwenmensch figurine from Wikimedia Commons/Dagmar Hollmann. Trowel from HiClipart. Neanderthal skull from Wikimedia Commons/DrMikeBaxter. Boxgrove handaxe from Krist Vaesen on ResearchGate. Wheat from dlpng.com. Lascaux panorama from thalo artist community. Neolithic house from <https://blog.stonehenge-stone-circle.co.uk/>. Cardium pottery from <https://forwhattheywerewear.wordpress.com/>. Newspaper from StickPNG. Megalithic silhouette from CLEANPNG.

READINGS

- Ambrose, S. H. (2001). Paleolithic technology and human evolution. *Science*, 291(5509), 1748-1753. DOI: 10.1126/science.1059487
- Ashmore, W., & Sharer, R.J. (2010). Reconstructing the past. In *Discovering Our Past: A Brief Introduction to Archaeology* (5th ed., pp. 178-210). Boston, MA: McGraw Hill.
- Bahn, P. (1998). Neanderthals emancipated. *Nature*, 394: 719-721. doi: 10.1038/29392.
- Bogaard, A., Charles, M., Twiss, K. C., Fairbairn, A., Yalman, N., Filipović, D., Arzu Demirergi, G., Ertuğ, F., Russell, N., & Henecke, J. (2009). Private pantries and celebrated surplus: Storing and sharing food at Neolithic Çatalhöyük, Central Anatolia. *Antiquity*, 83(321), 649-668. doi: 10.1017/S0003598X00098896
- Diamond, J. (1987). The worst mistake in the history of the human race. *Discover*, 91-93.
- Earle, T., Ling, J., Uhnér, C., Stos-Gale, Z., & Melheim, L. (2015). The Political Economy and Metal Trade in Bronze Age Europe: Understanding Regional Variability in Terms of Comparative Advantages and Articulations. *European Journal of Archaeology*, 18(4), 633-657. doi: 10.1179/1461957115y.0000000008
- Edwards, R., Schultz, M., Bucher, D., & Bradley, D.T. (2016). *Going to the Source: A Guide to Academic Integrity and Attribution at Vassar College*. Retrieved from: <https://deanofthecollege.vassar.edu/documents/sources/VassarGoingToTheSource.pdf>
- García Sanjuán, L., Triviño, M. L., Schuhmacher, T. X., Wheatley, D., & Banerjee, A. (2013). Ivory craftsmanship, trade and social significance in the southern Iberian Copper Age: The evidence from the PP4-Montelirio Sector of Valencina de la Concepción (Seville, Spain). *European Journal of Archaeology*, 16(4), 610-635. doi:10.1179/1461957113Y.0000000037
- Graff, G., & Birkenstein, C. (2006). *“They Say/I Say”: The Moves That Matter in Academic Writing*. New York, NY: W.W. Norton & Company.
- Grayson, D. & Delpech, F. (2002) Specialized early Upper Paleolithic hunters in southwestern France? *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 29(12): 1439-1449. doi: 10.1006/jasc.2002.0806
- Finn, C. (2001). Mixed messages: Archaeology and the media. *Public Archaeology*, 1:261-268. doi: 10.1179/pua.2001.1.4.261
- Hastorf, C. (2016). Preface. In *The Social Archaeology of Food: Thinking About Eating from Prehistory to the Present* (pp. xiii-xv). Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.

- Hastorf, C. (2016). The archaeological study of food activities. In *The Social Archaeology of Food: Thinking About Eating from Prehistory to the Present* (pp. 83-141). Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- Holtorf, C. (2002). Notes on the Life History of a Pot Sherd. *Journal of Material Culture*, 7(1): 49-71. doi: 10.1177/1359183502007001305.
- Larsen, C.S. (2006). The agricultural revolution as environmental catastrophe: Implications for health and lifestyle in the Holocene. *Quaternary International*, 150, 12-20. doi: 10.1016/j.quaint.2006.01.004
- Larsen, C.S. (2018). Bioarchaeology. *International Encyclopedia of Biological Anthropology*. doi: 10.1002/9781118584538.ieba0052
- Lieberman, C. (2019, March 25). Why you procrastinate (it has nothing to do with self-control). *The New York Times*. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/03/25/smarter-living/why-you-procrastinate-it-has-nothing-to-do-with-self-control.html>.
- Loubser, J.H.N. (2003). Of pothunters and pots. In *Archaeology: The Comic* (pp.1-26). Walnut Creek, CA: Altamira Press.
- Meyer, C., Brandt, G., Haak, W., Ganslmeier, R. A., Meller, H., & Alt, K. W. (2009). The Eulau eulogy: Bioarchaeological interpretation of lethal violence in Corded Ware multiple burials from Saxony-Anhalt, Germany. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 28(4), 412-423. doi: 10.1016/j.jaa.2009.07.002
- Parker Pearson, M. (2009). Placing the dead. In *The archaeology of death and burial* (pp. 124-141). Stroud, England: The History Press.
- Price, T.D. (2013). The Creative Explosion. In *Europe Before Rome: A Site-by-Site Tour of the Stone, Bronze, and Iron Ages* (pp. 56-122). Oxford, England: Oxford University Press.
- Price, T.D. (2013). Bronze Age Warriors. In *Europe Before Rome: A Site-by-Site Tour of the Stone, Bronze, and Iron Ages* (pp. 218-296). Oxford, England: Oxford University Press.
- Renfrew, C., & Bahn, P. (2018). Searching for the past: The history of archaeology. In *Archaeology Essentials: Theories/Methods/Practice* (4th ed., pp. 10-37). London: Thames & Hudson.
- Renfrew, C., & Bahn, P. (2018). What is left? The variety of the evidence. In *Archaeology Essentials: Theories/Methods/Practice* (4th ed., pp. 38-61). London: Thames & Hudson.

- Rocks-Macqueen, D. (2014, August 18). Archaeology and the press part 1—why does the news get it so, so, so, wrong? Retrieved from <https://dougsarchaeology.wordpress.com/2014/08/18/archaeology-and-the-press-part-1-why-does-the-news-get-it-so-so-so-wrong/>
- Savage, V., & Yeh, P. (2019). Tips from a Pulitzer Prizewinner. *Nature*, 574: 441-442.
- Speth, J. (2004). News flash: Negative evidence convicts Neanderthals of gross mental incompetence. *World Archaeology* 36(4): 519-526. doi: 10.1080/0043824042000303692
- Redding, R.W. (2005). Breaking the mold: A consideration of variation in the evolution of animal domestication. In J.-D Vigne, J. Peters & D. Helmer (Eds.), *First Steps of Animal Domestication: New Archaeozoological Approaches* (pp. 41-48). Oxford: Oxbow Books.
- Stringer, C. & Davies, W. (2001). Those elusive Neanderthals. *Nature* 413: 791-792. doi: 10.1038/35101688.
- Trigger, B. (2006). The beginnings of prehistoric archaeology. In *A History of Archaeological Thought* (2nd ed., pp. 121-166). Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- Vander Linden, M. (2016). Population history in third-millennium-BC Europe: assessing the contribution of genetics. *World Archaeology*, 48(5), 714-728. doi: 10.1080/00438243.2016.1209124